

Management

GREEN MARKETING –GO GREEN FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PUBLIC

J. Kavitha ^{*1}

^{*1} M.Phil. Research scholar, Department of Management Studies, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, INDIA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.59369

ABSTRACT

Environment plays an important role in our lives. The Humans are only responsible for the environment. The initiatives should be taken from every individual then the day is not so far when global warming could be controlled. In the phrase “GREEN MARKETING” green signifies eco-friendly innovation. The objective of this study is to examine the growth of green marketing sector & its future. The concept of green marketing is originated primarily in the developed markets and rapidly gaining scope in developing countries as well.

Keywords:

Green Marketing, Eco-Friendly & Eco- Labeling.

Cite This Article: J. Kavitha, “GREEN MARKETING –GO GREEN FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PUBLIC”, International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah, Vol. 4, No. 7: SE (2016): 40-43.

1. INTRODUCTION

Green Marketing is an eco-friendly idea for the need for quality, performance affordable pricing and convenience without having a detrimental effect on environment. It is primarily an idea towards planet earth that produces a product or service that may be friendly or is being manufactured in an eco-friendly way. The process of adding initiative towards the “GREENNESS” as the benefit, but not so real assumption of green marketing, is that consumer would be willing to pay more.

2. GREEN PRODUCTS

Money towards green products then towards normal products is seen different from the human point of view where every human wants to live in a healthy surrounding. Planet earth is facing a major challenge of global warming. Green marketing concept is very much alike the green plants that provide oxygen which is the basic need of living so if every person on this planet prefers a

green product, then the day will not be far when we actually save our earth. Green Marketing incorporates a broad range of activities starting from modification of product and packaging. In simple terms, it refers to the process of selling products and services based on their environmental benefits such a product may be environmental friendly by it.

The American Marketing Association defines green marketing as a three way definition:

- Retailing definition
- Social marketing definition
- Environmental definition

RETAILING DEFINITION

The marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe.

SOCIAL MARKETING DEFINITION

The development and marketing of products designed to minimize negative effects on physical environment and to improve its quality.

ENVIRONMENTAL DEFINITION

The efforts by organization to produce, promote, package and reclaim products in a manner that is sensitive or responsible to ecological concerns. Green marketing sectors not only opens the gate for adding values to the product modification but also the advertising which is now a day's direct means of adding customers towards green marketing.

3. HISTORY OF GREEN MARKETING

Green marketing was given prominence in late 1980's and 1990's after the first workshop on ecological marketing held in Austin. Today's world is the era of recyclable, non-toxic and environmental friendly goods. This has become a latest new mantra for marketers to satisfy the consumer needs and earn better, keeping in mind that consumer is everything. khanna et al. World Journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences

First phase: Ecological Green marketing, during the phase of all activities of marketing revolves mainly around the environment problems.

Second phase: Environmental Green marketing, focus gets shifted to clean technology to develop new products that take care of waste issues and pollution.

Third phase: Sustainable Green marketing, a paradigm shift relating to modern marketing concepts and practices.

4. WHY GREEN?

Human beings are the most acquisitive creature created by God who wants to fulfill his unlimited wants with limited resources. Market societies offer freedom of choice where any consumer can make his choice while buying. In order to comply with the limited resources. Sometimes, it is hard to face the reality, especially when the dream is so alluring, even where green products do seem to be selling its not primarily because of environment benefit. The term Green should not be confused with the public service campaigns aimed at getting people to change habits and adapt a more environment consciousness changing habits. Environmental

concerns as a source of competitive advantage, believe in moral obligation to be socially responsible. Government bodies mandate firms to implement eco-friendly systems that are why green marketing in contrast is aimed at getting people to buy stuff that is better for environment.

THE 4 GREEN P's

- Green Product
- Green Price
- Green Place
- Green Promotion

Green Product: Attributes such as energy saving, organic in nature etc. That leads to reduction in resource consumption and pollution.

Green Price: Most consumers will pay additional value if there is a perception of extra product value.

Green Place: Aiming to reduce carbon footprint by way of managing logistics to cut down transport emanations.

Green Promotion: To address the relationship between a product and environment to promote green life style and to present a corporate image of environmental responsibility.

5. ECO-LABELING

In India the government has introduced the eco-mark scheme since 1981. Eco-labeling provides information regarding the environmental performance of products. The objective of labeling is to provide authenticate ion to genuine claims regarding the environmental impact of products and processes by manufacturers.

ECO-LABELING SCHEME'S IN INDIA

The Ministry of environment and forests of the Government of India has prescribed the criteria for products as follows.

- That they are substantially less pollution than comparable products in production, usage and disposal.
- That they are recycled or recyclable whereas comparable products are not.
- That they contribute to a reduction on adverse environmental health consequences.
- That they comply with laws, standards and regulations pertaining to the environment.
- That their price is not exorbitantly higher than comparable products.

6. ECO-MARK IN INDIA

The Eco-Mark scheme awards products which are less harmful to the environment or have impact on environment through the various stages of development – manufacture, packaging, distribution, use and disposal or recycling. An earthen pot has been chosen as the logo for Eco-Mark scheme in India. The familiar earthen pot, a renewable resource like earth, does not produce hazardous waste and consumes little energy in making as a symbol it puts across its environmental message. Its image has the ability to reach people and helps to promote a greater

awareness of the need to be kind to the environment. The logo Eco-Mark scheme signifies that the product which carries it does least damage to the environment.

7. INNOVATIVE STEPS TOWARDS GREEN MARKETING

Starting with ONGC, Reliance, TATA group and other organizations such as ICICI, Idea Cellular, Vodafone, Videocon, Carrier, and Nokia etc. have joined the bandwagon. India is the world leader in green IT. Wipro Green is the first Indian company to launch eco-friendly range of desktops. Hindustan Unilever limited is trying to reduce its carbon foot print using modified machines in its production units similarly Hyderabad Airport, ITC –welcome group, Infosys, TCS, Agilent, HP, IBM are other organization all claiming to be going green. The Capital city New Delhi was being polluted at a very fast pace until the Supreme court of India forced a change to alternative fuels. In 2002, a directive was issued to completely adopt CNG in all public transport systems to curb pollution.

8. CONCLUSION

Being green is the need of the hour as resources on the mother earth are getting depleted day by day. Green manufacturing is a major consumer phenomenon and it is a paradigm shift from conventional marketing culture. Green Marketing looks at how marketing utilizes the resources which are limited while satisfying consumers unlimited wants as well as the industry. Green marketing is a good way to market products but only if it is done in a right way. The firms cannot lead to green marketing revolution unless the consumers get involved in thinking green. The desire should be to do what we admire doing and interpret things keeping in mind conservation and saving planet earth. Being green is no longer just an ethical choice it is also a business necessity. Loving nature is only the way to save our planet earth. Saving fuel, saving water, saving the planet is entirely in the hands of humans to protect the planet making every day the Earth Day.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] www.scribd.com/doc/57900742/Green-Mktg-in-India-2
- [2] www.suzlon.com
- [3] www.tata.com/company/articleinside/green-strategies
- [4] www.tnpl.com/Displaypage.aspx?file=environmental.htm
- [5] <http://www.eai.in/green../> India's-first-solar-powered-atm-Indus ind bank
- [6] www.greenmarketing.tv/2010/.../how.ceres-is-helping-businesses-go-green.
- [7] Regi, S. B., & Golden, S. A. R. (2014). *A Descriptive Study on the Role of Consumer Psychology and Behaviour in Product Purchasing*. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 3(12), 1-6.
- [8] books.google.co.in/books? *Isbn =160509868X Jacquelyn Ottman-2011-business & Economics*
- [9] www.hp.com/hpinfo/global/citizenship/environment.
- [10] 10. Golden, S. A. R. *MOBILE SUBSCRIBERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS SERVICE TARIFF WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TUTICORIN DIST*, *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*.